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DISTRIBUTION AND PHYTOCOENOSIS OF *LEPIDIUM LATIFOLIUM* L. SPECIES IN THE FLORA OF THE NAKHCHIVAN AUTONOMOUS REPUBLIC

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Abstract

Article *Brassicaceae* Burnett. is distributed in the flora of Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic. The distribution areas of *Lepidium latifolium* L. species belonging to *Lepidium* L. family are discussed and phytocoinosis is mentioned. Here, the coordinates, biological and ecological characteristics of the areas where *Lepidium latifolium* L. species is distributed are given based on GPS data. The

Keywords: *Lepidium latifolium* L., *Brassicaceae* Burnett., family, genus, species, plant.

Introduction

Plants are one of the most important and diverse groups in the living world. They are the main energy source of ecosystems and play an important role in maintaining the natural balance. For this purpose, the distribution, characteristics, distribution areas and role in nature of *Lepidium latifolium* L. species belonging to *Brassicaceae* Burnett. family were investigated in the flora of Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic.

Materials and methods: Boyahmad district of Culfa district and Batabat and Kuku districts of Shahbuz district were selected as the study area. The altitude zones and coordinates of the research area were determined using GPS. The research object is *Lepidium latifolium* L. belonging to the genus *Lepidium* L. of the family *Brassicaceae* Burnett. Plant samples were collected and herbarium was established in the research area. Species were identified using various identifiers.

Discussion:

Representatives of the *Brassicaceae* Burnett. family have a unique role in the formation of various local floras. This section includes wild and cultivated plants with various life forms. The genus *Lepidium* L. is represented by 12 species in Azerbaijan and 10 species in the flora of Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic [1; p.183-184, 7; p.154]: *Lepidium campestre* (L.) R.Br., *Lepidium coronopifolium* Fisch. ex Ledeb.(*L. lyratum* L.), *Lepidium crassifolium* Waldst. & Kit., *Lepidium draba* L., *Lepidium lacerum* C.A. Mey. (*L. persicum* Boiss.), *Lepidium latifolium* L., *Lepidium perfoliatum* L., *Lepidium ruderae* L., *Lepidium sativum* L., and *Lepidium vesicarium* L. Species of the genus *Lepidium* L. are distributed in countries with temperate and subtropical climates. Species of the genus are distributed on stony, rocky slopes of plains, agricultural lands, roadsides and ditches up to the central mountain belt of Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic. Species of the genus are annual, biennial and perennial herbaceous plants. *Lepidium sativum* L., belonging to the genus *Lepidium* L., is cultivated as a vegetable plant. The species of the genus *Lepidium lacerum* C.A. Mey. (*L. persicum* Boiss) is typical for Nakhchivan flora of Azerbaijan [1; p.184]. *Lepidium latifolium* L. is a perennial herb 40-120 cm tall. The leaves below the stem are ovate, lanceolate, those on the stem are toothed, while

the leaves above are lanceolate, almost sessile, vaguely toothed or entire. The plant produces white flowers in may and june. *Lepidium latifolium* L. is widespread as a weed in humid areas of the lowland and central mountain belt, in saline meadows and sometimes in fields and gardens. *Lepidium latifolium* L. is known as an important plant due to its ethnic value as a phyton [6; p.84]. Consumption of Brassica (Cruciferae) vegetables is associated with a reduced risk of cancer, but identification of the active components and insights into the underlying molecular events are scarce. Here we found that an extract of *Lepidium latifolium*, a cruciferous plant native to southern Europe, Mediterranean countries and Asia, showed in vitro cytotoxic activity, inducing caspase-dependent apoptosis, in a variety of human tumor cells, and the plant juice showed in vivo antitumor activity in a HT-29 human colon cancer xenograft mouse model [2; p. 347].

The survey area is the upper part of Kuku village in Shahbuz district - 1930 m (39°32'7"N, 45°37'5"E) and 1908 m (39°32'12"N, 45°37'2"E) and the road to Darabogaz - 1996 m (39°32'42"N), 45°36'32"E), 2074 m (39°32'52"N, 45°36'1"E), 2021 m (39°32'52"N, 45°35'49"E), 1995 m (39°32'39"N, 45°36'39"E) found *Lepidium latifolium* L. we have arrived. The phytocoenosis of *Lepidium latifolium* L. includes species such as *Lallemantia peltata* C.A. Mey., *Plantago minuta* Pall, *Secale sylvestre* Host., *Trifolium canescens* Willd.

In the Batabat area of the Shahbuz region at an altitude of 2219 m (39° 31', 59' N, 45° 47' 50" E), the lush herbaceous growth of *Lepidium latifolium* L. is joined by species such as *Rosa canina* L., *Papaver orientale* L., *Pyrethrum chiliophyllum* Fisch. & C.A.Mey., *Achillea millefolium* L., *Sinapis arvensis* L., *Lotus caucasicus* Kuprian. ex Juz., *Ranunculus arvensis* L., *Cirsium vulgare* (Savi) Ten., *Cichorium intybus* L., *Potentilla recta* L., *Stachys sylvatica* L., *Salvia armeniaca* (Bordz.) Grossh., *Tragopogon latifolius* Boiss., *Thymus rariflorus* C.Koch., *Trifolium alpestre* L., *Trifolium canescens* Willd., *Taraxacum montanum* (C.A.Mey.) D.C., *Verbascum orientale* (L.) All. (*Celsia orientalis* L.)).

We observed the distribution of *Lepidium latifolium* L. in Boyahmad village area of Julfa district at an

altitude of 2175 m. The composition of the phytocenosis containing the species is as follows: *Ranunculus arvensis* L., *Astragalus strictifolius* Boiss., *Crataegus pentagyna* Waldst. & Kit., *Pyrus salicifolia* Pall., *Papaver orientale* L., *Grammosciadium platycarpum* Boiss. & Hausskn., *Hypericum formosissimum* Takht.,

Equisetum arvense L., *Allium rubellum* Bieb. (*A. syntamanthum* C.Koch), *Artemisia vulgaris* L., *Trifolium alpestre* L., *Trifolium pratense* L., *Helichrysum callichrysum* DC., *Falcaria vulgaris* Bernh. [*F. siosides* (Wib.)Aschers.], *Eryngium campestre* L., *Phlomis orientalis* Mill., *Ferula percica* Willd., *Euphorbia orientalis* L., *Stachys germanica* L., *Iris caucasica* Stev.

Table

Analysis of species composition of phytocenosis, including *Lepidium latifolium* L. (Boyehamed area)

№	Familia	Genus	Species	Life form
1.	<i>Rosaceae</i> Juss.	<i>Crataegus</i> L.	<i>Crataegus pentagyna</i> Waldst. & Kit.	Tree
2.	<i>Rosaceae</i> Juss.	<i>Pyrus</i> L.	<i>Pyrus salicifolia</i> Pall.	Tree
3.	<i>Equisetaceae</i> Michx. ex DC.	<i>Equisetum</i> L.	<i>Equisetum arvense</i> L.	Perennial
4.	<i>Fabaceae</i> Lindl.	<i>Astragalus</i> L.	<i>Astragalus strictifolius</i> Boiss.	Bush
5.	<i>Fabaceae</i> Lindl.	<i>Trifolium</i> L.	<i>Trifolium alpestre</i> L.	Perennial
6.	<i>Fabaceae</i> Lindl.	<i>Trifolium</i> L.	<i>Trifolium pratense</i> L.	Perennial
7.	<i>Papaveraceae</i> Juss.	<i>Papaver</i> L.	<i>Papaver orientale</i> L.	Perennial
8.	<i>Hypericaceae</i> Juss.	<i>Hypericum</i> L.	<i>Hypericum formosissimum</i> Takht.	Perennial
9.	<i>Amaryllidaceae</i> J.St.-Hil.	<i>Allium</i> L.	<i>Allium rubellum</i> Bieb.	Perennial
10.	<i>Asteraceae</i> Bercht. & J.Presl	<i>Artemisia</i> L.	<i>Artemisia vulgaris</i> L.	Perennial
11.	<i>Asteraceae</i> Bercht. & J.Presl	<i>Helichrysum</i> Mill.	<i>Helichrysum callichrysum</i> DC.	Perennial
12.	<i>Apiaceae</i> Lindl.	<i>Grammosciadium</i> DC.	<i>Grammosciadium platycarpum</i> Boiss. & Hausskn.	Perennial
13.	<i>Apiaceae</i> Lindl.	<i>Falcaria</i> Fabr.	<i>Falcaria vulgaris</i> Bernh.	Biennial (sometimes perennial)
14.	<i>Apiaceae</i> Lindl.	<i>Eryngium</i> L.	<i>Eryngium campestre</i> L.	Perennial
15.	<i>Apiaceae</i> Lindl.	<i>Ferula</i> L.	<i>Ferula percica</i> Willd.	Perennial
16.	<i>Lamiaceae</i> Martinov	<i>Phlomis</i> L.	<i>Phlomis orientalis</i> Mill.	Perennial
17.	<i>Lamiaceae</i> Martinov	<i>Stachys</i> L.	<i>Stachys germanica</i> L.	Perennial
18.	<i>Euphorbiaceae</i> Juss.	<i>Euphorbia</i> L.	<i>Euphorbia orientalis</i> L.	Perennial
19.	<i>Iridaceae</i> Juss.	<i>Iris</i> L.	<i>Iris caucasica</i> Stev.	Perennial
20.	<i>Ranunculaceae</i> Juss.	<i>Ranunculus</i> L.	<i>Ranunculus arvensis</i> L.	Annual

According to the analysis of the table, the species in the phytocenosis are 2 species of trees, 1 species of bush, 15 species of perennials, one species of annuals and one species of biennial herbaceous plants according to their life forms. Here, 4 species belong to *Apiaceae* Lindl., 2 to *Rosaceae* Juss., 2 to *Fabaceae*

Lindl., 2 to *Asteraceae* Bercht & J. Presl, 2 to *Lamiaceae* Martinov (*Equisetaceae* Michx. ex DC., *Papaveraceae* Juss., *Hypericaceae* Juss., *Amaryllidaceae* J.St.-Hil., *Euphorbiaceae* Juss., *Iridaceae* Juss., *Ranunculaceae* Juss.) belong to one species.

Lepidium latifolium L.

Conclusion: The elevation zones and coordinates of the study area were determined. During the expedition to the regions, the distribution area and ecological environment of *Lepidium latifolium* L. were clarified. The species composition of the formation where the plant is located was analyzed. The formation in which *Lepidium latifolium* L. species is located contains mostly perennial species.

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